

A Study of the Effects of an Individual's Personality and Characteristics on Job Behavior Using the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator

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ABSTRACT- The Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality test is becoming increasingly commonly used and acknowledged in many fields as a way to identify personality, and some businesses are starting to implement it in many workplaces to assist businesses increase productivity. This study tries to describe the ways in which MBTI can be used to determine an individual's traits in work behaviours, especially when dealing with other people, tasks, assessments, and friendship prospects.

To come to a conclusion about how a person's personality and features affect their behaviour at work, this research uses an integrated method of literature review. For the purpose of understanding and interpreting this integrative literature study, numerous guidelines and case-based examples have been explored. It still has certain drawbacks, and there are just a few prior research. Future research in this area will be required to adapt.

KEYWORDS- Job Behaviour, Myers-Briggs Type Indicator, Performance, Personality Traits, Personality Assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the course of organizational development, personality is crucial. More people are paying attention to functioning more effectively as management develops. Herakleitos claimed in antiquity that fate is determined by personality.

Nowadays, a person's personality is a key factor in appraising them. A well-known personality test is the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI). It is most typically employed in a variety of contexts, including consulting, teaching, and administration. Nevertheless, only a small number of people pay attention to personality, a crucial component in management development. Numerous studies demonstrate how personality affects people's abilities in the workplace and in teams. This term paper focuses on how the MBTI is used to explore the connection between job satisfaction, job's behavior and personality characteristics.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

How inherent characteristics of an individual helps in determining his or her job behavior in four moderating variables of job situations, which are managing other

people, tasks, assessments / feedbacks and friendship possibilities ?

III. OBJECTIVES

- To investigate the relationship between personality factors, work features, and job satisfaction.
- To focus on the relative contributions of personality types, job characteristics, and their relationships.
- To understand the characteristics of an individual, as measured by MBTI.

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Since job satisfaction is linked to employee retention and organisational productivity, it is a crucial variable to track. Additionally, it evaluates corporate citizenship practises. These are described by Organ (1988) as "discretionary individual behaviour that improves the effective running of the organisation in the aggregate but is not directly or openly recognised by the formal incentive system." Because of the connection between these habits and job performance, employers should consider them when hiring new employees. There is a difference between organisational citizenship behaviours focused toward organisations and organisational citizenship behaviours directed toward individuals, it is crucial to remember this.

According to Argysis (1973), people look for careers that promote development and self-actualization. According to Strauss' (1974) theory, workers have two fundamentally different perspectives on their jobs: some see them as means to an end, while others use them to fulfil their needs for accomplishment and self-actualization. It is possible to divide the relationship between personality and job performance into two separate phases (Barrick, Mount, & Judge, 2001). From the turn of the century until the middle of the 1980s, research was done in the first phase (Barrick et al., 2001). Personnel selection experts were against using personality tests to choose employees (Hurtz & Donovan, 2000). Personality tests did not "show adequate, predictive variability to validate their use in personnel selection," according to the general result (Hurtz & Donovan, 2000). While a large body of research has shown that personality types and work features are associated to job happiness, relatively little study has

looked at the predictability of pleasure in currently held positions from personality type. According to some research, personality type may have the biggest impact on job selection. In fact, it seems that this association is rather universal across civilizations.

The interest in using personality tests to choose employees has increased in recent years. Paul D. Tieger explained how career counselors might use the MBTI to assist clients locate employment for which they are most qualified and likely to be fulfilled. Indeed, they think that one of the key elements to take into account while assisting a person in making job options is their personality type. An employee's job characteristics may determine the level of job satisfaction he or she actually experiences. The reason for this is that personality type may have the greatest influence on the choice of a career that an individual feels will be rewarding for them.

V. METHODOLOGY

The typical goal of this paper involves reviewing mixed viewpoints and insights from many fields or study traditions, hence it frequently necessitates a more inventive collection of data. Thereby, to discuss these established views, integrative literature review is used in this term paper. This study seeks to highlight how MBTI can be used to understand the individual's characteristics in the workplace, particularly in terms of job relations and satisfaction. Further, analysis is done on how these elements commonly affect the job behaviour. The profiling of these behaviours is diversified ahead with the help of a model consisting of 4 factors, where each factor uses one of the four major dimensions of MBTI personality type theory to process the behavioural outcome:

- Extrovert (E) vs. Introvert (I) personality types indicate how energetic a person is for his tasks / job role.
- How a person interprets information for his job characteristics is denoted by Sensing (S) vs. Intuition (N).
- An individual's decision-making process is decided by Thinking (T) vs. Feeling (F).
- The life-style a person adopts as per his job or how it administers job satisfaction can be understood by Judging (J) and Perceiving (P).

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Influence of Personality Characteristics in Workplace

The potential influences that personality characteristics may have on the work features, either directly or indirectly (through moderating factors) can be analyzed by below four identified variables:

- Managing other people
- Tasks
- Assessments / Feedbacks
- Friendship possibilities

B. How the individual types of MBTI of a person can have effects in the workplace according to the above four different variables

1) Extroversion:

The exterior world of people and things tends to capture the attention of those who favor extraversion. Extraverts like

change and activity. Extroverts are more adept at managing others since they are more externally minded. They frequently take up another coworker's time. They are also frequently adept at greeting others. Despite their distaste of complex processes and their impatience with lengthy, tedious tasks, they are interested in outcomes and feedback, whether they are obtained through interpersonal interactions or independently. Due to their more outwardness and willingness to make new friends, they frequently do not mind phone calls or "drop in" guests. They typically have good communication skills and like being around other people. Most extraverts have a "little" introvert inside looking for some quiet time vs. Introvert (I) personality types indicate how energetic a person is for his tasks / job role.

2) Introversion:

Because introversion are "inward" minded and appreciate the calm for concentration, those who live in the interior frequently let intrusions into their "time patch." Since they enjoy working alone and may find it difficult to communicate, such people seem to be hesitant while managing others. Most introverts also possess a "slight" extravert who needs attention. According to well-known individuals, most introverts are actually "little" extraverts looking for the spotlight. They have less opportunity to interact as a result, which lessens the likelihood of friendship. As a result of their preference for working alone, people may struggle to remember names and faces. As a result, they are able to work continuously on one project without growing bored. They may also "analyze first" and "work afterwards," despise phone interruptions and "drop in" visits, and generally care more about the concepts underlying their job than just the results. In their work in the office, they frequently pay attention to details.

3) Sensing:

Unless there are established solutions, sensing personality types typically dislike novel situations. They frequently have accurate feedback and assessments because they experience time as a concept that is genuine, present, and actual. They prefer to employ their existing talents rather than learning new ones, so they work consistently and have accurate time estimates. They often prefer to think things out thoroughly before coming to a decision, which helps them control impatient coworkers in challenging situations. Such individuals are careful with mundane details, which causes them to hardly ever believe inspirations and hardly ever commit factual errors. They excel in precise work as a result.

4) Intuitive:

Since intuitive people prefer to solve novel challenges and view time as a resource for conjecture or theorizing, they typically take longer to complete tasks. This is due to the fact that they frequently operate in short bursts of intense energy and enthusiasm interspersed with intervals of inactivity and are able to swiftly connect two things together while working continuously. They frequently get their facts slightly mixed up and are inclined to follow personal impulses, whether those impulses are good or bad, which can lead to either positive or negative feedback. This is because they prefer to learn new skills over using them. They detest repeating the exact thing several times. These workers are patient and appreciate challenging situations,

but they get impatient with mundane details and despise spending extra time being precise.

5) Thinking:

Since thoughtful people tend to be somewhat emotionless and unconcerned with other people's feelings, they are not the ideal human beings to oversee a team of workers. These professionals view time as something to calculate or measure in relation to finishing duties that can unintentionally offend people. They frequently make decisions impersonally and may get along without agreeing with others, occasionally disregarding their wishes. However, this same strategy aids them in analyzing and organizing information, which enables them to earn commendable evaluations and comments on the work they have completed. They must be treated decently, and when required, they can discipline others or make difficult judgments regarding them. They frequently struggle to connect with emotional types and might come out as cold-hearted, which hinders the development of meaningful relationships at work.

6) Feeling:

Feeling types often have a keen awareness of other people's emotions and view time as a relational or interpersonal activity, fostering healthy relationships inside organizations. They tend to prefer peace to such a length that office fights may hinder their productivity on duties. They enjoy pleasing people, even in small matters. They frequently allow their choices to be impacted by their personal or others' interests, therefore they take feedback very seriously. They require occasional praise but detest giving people harsh news or making difficult decisions about others, making them unsuitable for leading a team of others. However, they also have good interpersonal skills and prefer to be sympathetic.

7) Judging:

Judging personality types can organize their activities and follow a strategy, it makes it easier for them to efficiently complete their job. They view time as an asset to be managed and value orderly, completed tasks since they get positive feedback on their assessments. They could make decisions too rapidly and resent taking a break from a project they're currently working on to work on something more vital. They become too prejudiced toward their own tastes as a result, which is why they shouldn't be chosen to oversee a sizable workforce. They might not be aware of additional tasks that must be completed and may simply require the bare necessities while starting a task. Once they make a decision about anything, a circumstance, or a person, they frequently feel pleased, which leaves little to no room for friendship.

8) Perceptive:

The ability to adjust to changing circumstances and a willingness to leave things open to change make perceptive types ideal managers of employees of many types. They have a very flexible view of how time should be used and view it as something that may be added later. They could struggle with decision-making and have a propensity to start way too many initiatives. Due to their difficulties finishing projects and propensity to put off unpleasant chores, this causes mixed feedback. Before starting a new work, they want to learn everything about it. They have a

natural curiosity and frequently seek out more information.

C. Effects of the MBTI Personality Theory on Characteristics Of Job Behavior

Extrovert (E) vs. Introvert (I) personality types indicate how energetic a person is for his tasks / job role. It identifies an employee's preference for focusing their perception and judgment of assigned tasks either on their immediate subordinates (E) or their own inner ideas. (I). Introverts prefer the subjective experience of concepts and ideas in any tasks, whereas extroverts prefer the outer world of people and things and engage in groups to perform all the work related activities.

How a person interpreting information about their job is denoted by sensing (S) vs intuition (N). Sensing employees interpret hard data in facts accurately, concretely, and usefully. The situation's recognised facts are the center of attention for them as they have a propensity to isolate every aspect of a scenario and develop one notion. Employees of intuitive (N) senses regulate them so that instructions given by managers are absorbed as a whole to investigate the unknown and detect ramifications and possibilities that are not immediately obvious. They try to be creative by looking beyond the obvious facts. They tend to compare one circumstance to another and search out different interpretations and meanings within data provided.

A person's decision-making process is decided by thinking (T) vs. feeling (F). Managers who think (T) employ a logical, analytical method to arrive at reasoned conclusions or decisions, without taking personal aspects into account. When making decisions, a thinking manager will look for different courses of action, their potential costs and rewards, as well as the results of taking no action. After which, they then choose the optimal path of action. Managers with feeling (F) concentrate on making conclusions based on individualized and subjective values. In contrast to being logical, the emotion function is a way of decision-making that is focused on issues of fairness and ethics. This entails thinking about a choice in terms of personal stakes of the people and groups the choice will affect. The feeling type of manager evaluates the values associated with each choice, how employees will respond, and whether the most likely outcome will improve outcomes for both individuals and groups in decision-making situations. Managers with such orientations are the one who forms close, caring relationships with staff members and values their efforts.

The life-style a person adopts as per his job can be understood by judging (J) and perceiving (P). These personality types are related to how someone likes to interact with other people and the outside world. Judges favor leading a planned, structured life. They favor meticulously planning and managing their life. Perceivers favor an adaptable, unplanned lifestyle. They try to comprehend and cope with life.

VII. CONCLUSION

As a result of people being drawn to and chosen by organisations based on their personalities, it is possible that distinct personality types end up at different organisations, hence personality may not have arisen as a substantial predictor of an individual's behaviour in an organisation. However, at the stage of organisational entry, the likelihood

of each person's behaviour in relation to their work functions should be roughly equal. Other aspects, such as a person's particular attributes, start to impact their behaviour in a company when they acquire experience in the new role. As shown by the present study's findings, a number of personality trait factors eventually start to matter when attempting to anticipate how traits would affect a person's conduct at work. Although people are free to govern themselves in any work environment, their behaviour on the job will always reflect the intrinsic traits of their individual personalities. Although it is presumed that personalities remain consistent, it would not be unreasonable to believe that as people get more established in their careers, their personalities alter with time.

VIII. LIMITATIONS

1) The variables considered in the section "Influence of personality characteristics in the workplace" are irrespective of gender, salary, number of jobs held previously and variety of work performed.

2) Loss of consistency, correctness, and bias are caused by the mix and complication of integrating conclusions from papers using several approaches.

IX. FUTURE STUDY

This study can be conducted using secondary data on a number of positions held by a sample inside an organisation. Without regard to employment, organisation, or work type, the study of participant responses can be used to identify which of the individual's variables are significant in influencing job behaviour for each MBTI.

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